

POLYPHEM
THE FUTURE OF SMALL-SCALE CSP PLANTS

POLYPHEM

Small-Scale Solar Thermal Combined Cycle

D7.3 Report on performance assessment and model validation

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Background: about the POLYPHEM project

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The POLYPHEM project is a research and innovation action funded by the European Union's H2020 program. It is implemented by a European consortium of 4 research centres and 5 industrial partners. The aim is to increase the flexibility and improve the performance of small solar tower power plants. The concept of POLYPHEM consists in implementing a combined cycle formed by a solarized micro gas-turbine and an Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC) machine, with an integrated thermal storage device between the two cycles. The need for cooling is minimal.

Developed from a patented technology by CNRS and CEA, the pressurized air solar receiver is integrated in the micro-turbine cycle. The thermal efficiency targeted for the receiver is 80% with a cost of 400 €/kW. The innovative thermal storage uses a thermal oil and a single thermocline tank with a technical concrete filler material.

The main expected impact of this project is to enhance the competitiveness of low-carbon energy production systems through the technology developed. The expected progress is a better fitting of electricity generation to variable local needs, an overall conversion efficiency of solar energy into electricity of 18% for an investment cost of less than 5 €/W and a low environmental impact. By 2030, the cost of electricity production targeted by the POLYPHEM technology is 165 €/MWh for an annual direct normal irradiation of 2600 kWh/m²/year (North Africa and Middle East) and 209 €/MWh under 2050 kWh/m²/year (Southern Europe). In addition to decentralized power generation, other applications are considered for the deployment of this technology used in poly-generation: industrial heat production, solar heating and cooling, desalination of seawater or brackish water.

The objective of the project is to validate the technical choices under test conditions representative of actual operating conditions.

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Table of content

1.	INTRODUCTION	8
2.	PRINCIPLE OF SIMULATION TOOLS	8
3.	DESCRIPTION OF COMPONENT MODELS	10
3.1	Heliostat Field	10
3.2	Pressurized Air Receiver	10
3.3	Micro Gas Turbine	11
3.4	Heat Exchanger	14
3.5	Organic Rankine Cycle	14
3.6	Stratified Thermal Energy Storage	14
4.	PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT AND VALIDATION	16
4.1	Heliostat Field Model	16
4.2	Pressurized Air Receiver Model	17
4.3	Micro Gas Turbine Model	22
4.4	Heat Exchanger Model	24
4.5	Organic Rankine Cycle Model	25
4.6	Stratified Thermal Storage Model	26
5.	CONCLUSION	29
6.	REFERENCES	30

List of figures:

Figure 1: Exemplary visualization of Raytrace3D model of a heliostat field	9
Figure 2: Scene in Raytrace3D for the THEMIS system using the whole heliostat field.	10
Figure 3: POLYPHEM panel with Ni-based alloy frame, copper matrix and multi-layered tubes.	11
Figure 4: Proposed Operating line and comparison with previous model in a Pressure.....	13
Figure 5: Proposed Operating line and comparison with previous model in a Efficiency	14
Figure 6: Sensitivity analysis for the optical efficiency at design point	16
Figure 7: POLYPHEM - Heliostat field layout and optical efficiency for 40 m (left) and 100 m (right) tower heights. Attention: colour ranges for optical efficiency are not equal!.....	17
Figure 8: POLYPHEM - Resulting flux concentration map in the receiver surface for two exemplary moments of low DNI (left) and high DNI (right).....	17
Figure 9: Sensitivity analysis for the pressure drop in the POLYPHEM receiver without twisted tapes (left) and with twisted tapes (right).	18
Figure 10: Sensitivity analysis for wall temperature in the POLYPHEM receiver without twisted tapes (left) and with twisted tapes (right).	19
Figure 11: Pressured drop for different total number of tubes and rows for 0.9 m tube length (left) and 1 m tube length (right)	20
Figure 12: Maximum wall temperature for different total number of tubes and rows for 0.9 m tube length (left) and 1 m tube length (right).....	20
Figure 13: POLYPHEM Receiver efficiency for different total number of tubes and rows for 0.9 m tube length (left) and 1 m tube length (right).	21
Figure 14: Distributions of the pressurized air bulk temperature, pressurized air film temperature, absorber surface temperature, and radiation concentration on the front surface for the optimized POLYPHEM receiver configuration for two exemplary moments of low DNI (left) and high DNI (right).....	22
Figure 15: Comparison of the performance map data used in the model and the data provided by the manufacturer.....	23
Figure 16: Comparison of the performance map data used in the model and the experimental	23
Figure 17: POLYPHEM - μ GT performance parameters as a function of heat rate absorbed.	24
Figure 18: POLYPHEM - Comparison of the calculation obtained in ColSim CSP and Epsilon of the power of μ GT subcomponents under variable speed approach.	24
Figure 19: Result of the design point simulation of RHX for two exemplary days.	25
Figure 20: Result of the off-design point simulation of RHX for two exemplary days.....	25
Figure 21: POLYPHEM - ORC performance in response to variation of Input thermal power. Fluctuation.....	26
Figure 22: POLYPHEM - ORC performance as a function of ambient temperature	26
Figure 23: Validation with experimental data of the charging process from 180°C to 250°C with mass flow of 0.2 kg/s (top left), 0.3 kg/s (top right), 0.45 kg/s (bottom left) and 0.9 kg/s (bottom right).	28
Figure 24: Validation with experimental data of the discharging process from 180°C to 110°C with mass flow of 0.2 kg/s (top left), 0.9 kg/s (top right), 0.4 kg/s (bottom left) and 0.6 kg/s (bottom right).	28

List of tables:

Table 1: Parameters for the sensitivity analysis of the heliostat field.....	16
Table 2: Parameters for the sensitivity analysis of the solar receiver	18
Table 3: Parameter modification for modelling dual-media region (TES zone only).....	26
Table 4: Simulation parameters for validation of the stratified thermal storage with Microsol-R data.	27

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym/abbreviation	Meaning/full text
μ GT	Micro Gas Turbine
AALB	Aalborg CSP
ARRA	Arraela S.L.
CA	Consortium Agreement
CEA	Commissariat à l’Energie Atomique
CIEMAT	Centro de Investigaciones Energeticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
CO	Confidential: only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
Colsim CSP	Dynamic simulation tool used for the second step of the OPTIPHEM toolchain
CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
D	Deliverable
DevISE	Proprietary tool of Fraunhofer ISE
DNI	Direct Normal Irradiation
Ebsilon	Commercial software EBSILON® Professional
EU	European Union
EURO	Euronovia
FISE	Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems, ISE
HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid
KAE	Kaefer Isoliertechnik GmbH
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Electricity
LCOH	Levelized Cost of Heat
M	Month
MS	Milestone
Nu	Nusselt number
OPTIPHEM	Tool chain developed by Fraunhofer ISE
ORC	‘Orcan Energy AG’ or ‘Organic Rankine Cycle’
PU	Public
TES	Thermal Energy Storage
WP	Work Package
μ GT	Micro Gas Turbine

1. INTRODUCTION

To improve the flexibility and performance of small-scale concentrated solar power (CSP) plants, the POLYPHEM project proposes a new technology: a solar-driven combined cycle with integrated thermal energy storage. The baseline technology consists of an air Brayton cycle as top cycle and an organic Rankine cycle (ORC) as bottom cycle. POLYPHEM broadens this technology by driving the top cycle with solar energy through the development of an advanced technology of pressurized air solar receiver, and by including an innovative thermocline energy storage and a recovery heat exchanger between both cycles.

For optimally designing such a system and to analyse its annual performance, simulation tools are needed. For this optimization, Fraunhofer ISE has developed the OPTIPHEM tool chain which combines design, simulation, optimization and LCOE calculation tools specifically to model and optimize the design for a small-scale POLYPHEM-like CSP plant, since the available commercial tools for CSP plant simulations are often restricted to large-scale power plants. This tool has been based on POLYPHEM technology with the possibility of scaling the size of the plant in terms of ambient conditions, the electrical power output, or the capacity of storage. Therefore, the specific performance of each component and the overall performance has been assessed.

This report focuses on the validation and adaptation of the component models that were developed for the OPTIPHEM tool chain. The preliminary models were tuned with data provided by the partners of the project, and some components were validated with measurement data.

2. PRINCIPLE OF SIMULATION TOOLS

The component models have been developed in three different proprietary tools of Fraunhofer ISE for different purposes.

- The preliminary design of the power plant is carried out in devISE_{CSP}. In this first step, all component sizes and characteristics are defined based on the desired nominal power block (based on characteristics of small-scale plants) conditions, plant location and storage hours.
- The optical simulation is performed in Raytrace3D for calculating the annual performance and the transient behavior of the optical components.
- The dynamic hourly simulation of the plant is performed based on a system model in ColSim CSP, that determines the electricity output of all possible component sizes of the plant.

2.1.1 [DevISE_{CSP}](#)

In order to analyze the design process of a possible future commercial plant, it is necessary to define the principal characteristics and the layout of such system. The Fraunhofer in-house tool, devISE_{CSP}, was created to perform fast design calculations of CSP systems. The tool is structured in modules of Python code that design components or processes of the plant. These modules are component models based on steady state thermodynamic equations. Each component design model is a Python function that determines – with the given inputs – the most relevant parameters for the basic design, such as size, capacity, and efficiency. The tool enables the user to create different configurations of the existing components and modify the sizes adjusting to the system requirements and boundary conditions.

2.1.2 [Raytrace3D](#)

Raytrace3D is a Fraunhofer ISE in-house software suite that is used for the assessment and optimization of concentrating collectors. The first development of the software suite dates back more than ten years, when a first two-dimensional approach was implemented for line-focusing collectors (Mertins 2009). Later, the concept was extended to three dimensions and the program obtained its name Raytrace3D. By continuous

development it is adapted and constantly improved to fit the needs of project like POLYPHEM. The simulation engine itself and the pre-/post-processing tools are implemented with a performant yet flexible combination of C/C++ and Python. A comprehensive library of geometries, materials, volumetric materials, and light sources is included that suits the needs of heliostat field/receiver modeling in POLYPHEM. As opposed to rendering engines (backward ray tracing), Raytrace3D uses a forward ray tracing approach (Schöttl et al. 2022). An exemplary ray tracing scene for heliostat field is displayed in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1: Exemplary visualization of Raytrace3D model of a heliostat field

2.1.3 ColSim CSP

ColSim CSP is the Fraunhofer ISE in-house system simulation software that performs transient yield assessment based on annual simulations. It was initially designed by Christof Wittwer in 1999 (Christof Wittwer 1999) and continuously developed and used at Fraunhofer ISE subsequently. ColSim CSP can perform dynamic thermohydraulic system simulations and allows for the integration of complex control strategies. Based on modules of C and C++ codes, it presents an adaptable and flexible interface for the modelling and simulation of different technical systems. From the ColSim CSP library, the necessary components such as pumps, heat exchangers, pipes or solar receivers can be chosen and linked together in line with the POLYPHEM technology.

3. DESCRIPTION OF COMPONENT MODELS

3.1 HELIOSTAT FIELD

In the heliostat field model, first, the staggered layout of the mirrors is defined. The rows of the heliostat field are created with a constant spacing between them, defined by the size of the mirrors and a minimum distance defined by the user. The radial distance between the rows is calculated according to the no-blocking condition, meaning that the reflected sun rays from a heliostat are not blocked by a neighbouring heliostat before arriving to the receiver. The heliostat field design model creates a field layout for maximum overall optical efficiency. The optical efficiency is strongly dependant on the relative position of the mirrors from the sun and the receiver, so it depends on the tower height and the sun position. This field is optimized by selecting the best performing heliostat mirrors, able to generate the desired power output.

Subsequently, the Fraunhofer ISE in-house tool *Raytrace3D* is used for the simulation of the flux distribution on the receiver surfaces. The assessment is performed transiently with sky discretization (Schöttl et al. 2016) and flux map/load level interpolation (Schöttl et al. 2018). The load level interpolation method includes the defocusing due to flux limits. Furthermore, the MIRVAL atmospheric attenuation model (Leary und Hankins 1979) has been used together with the Buie sun shape distribution (Buie et al. 2003) with parametrized circumsolar ratio. Heliostat tracking and surface slope errors are modeled with perturbed surfaces normal following a Gaussian distribution and its standard deviation is parametrized.

Within the POLYPHEM project, the THEMIS heliostat field was taken as a reference basis. The ray tracing was performed based on the detailed information provided by CNRS. The positions of the individual heliostats were provided in a coordinate system relative to the tower. The heliostats have been modeled on facet level, individual canting and individual focal lengths for each heliostat have been considered as defined by CNRS. *Figure 2* shows a ray tracing scene for the THEMIS system using the whole heliostat field.

Figure 2: Scene in Raytrace3D for the THEMIS system using the whole heliostat field.

3.2 PRESSURIZED AIR RECEIVER

The core technology developed is a bundle of thin nickel-based alloy tubes arranged in parallel rows and embedded into copper, which is a highly conductive material. A twisted tape insert of the same nickel-based alloy will be introduced inside the tubes in order to enhance the heat transfer fluid with the pressurized air, see *Figure 3*. It has been shown that twisted tape inserts increase the heat transfer coefficient substantially

with a relatively small pressure-drop loss (Manglik und Bergles 1993). An external thin plate of nickel-based alloy prevents oxidation and corrosion of the copper structure.

Figure 3: POLYPHEM panel with Ni-based alloy frame, copper matrix and multi-layered tubes.

When designing the POLYPHEM pressurized air receiver, there are three main constraints that must be considered. First, a maximum pressure drop of 5%, which is crucial for the performance of the micro gas turbine. The pressure drop in the receiver would reduce the pressure difference in expansion and directly impact the power output. Second, the temperature on the irradiated surface of the solar receiver should not exceed 1000°C. The temperature constraint is directly related with the material selected for the front layer, the tubes and the inserts. In this case, a nickel-based alloy 600 and alloy 230 were selected because of their physical and mechanical properties. Finally, since the irradiated flux from the heliostat field has a circular shape, in order to avoid mechanical strains, the receiver shape should be close to a square. In other words, the aspect ratio of the receiver, which is the height divided by the length, should be maintained close to 1. The design of the receiver is optimized for the needed power output considering these constraints.

For pressure drop in the receiver tubes is given by the Darcy–Weisbach equation (Nevers 1970). For the friction factor, the effect of the twisted tape inserts has to be taken into account (Kreith et al. 2011). To calculate the heat transfer in the solar receiver, the different thermal resistances have been evaluated. Considering the geometry of the receiver, four main resistances were identified: conduction resistance of the front nickel-based alloy wall, conduction resistance of the copper frame, conduction resistance of the nickel-based alloy tubes, and finally, the convective resistance between the tubes and the pressurized air coming from the compressor. Once the heat transfer inside the receiver is defined, the temperature of the wall, tubes and air are determined. More detailed information of the calculations for designing the receiver can be found in (Ferrerres 2021).

For the system simulation, the thermo-hydraulic receiver model makes use of transient flux maps on receiver surfaces and takes into account natural and forced convection on the receiver (Schöttl et al. 2020), also incorporating the influence of wind. Based on view factors (from ray tracing) and \hat{F} -factors (for modelling secondary reflections (Teichel et al. 2012)), the reflection and radiative heat transfer of the receiver are assessed. The receiver model is integrated with the other plant components in the system model in ColSim CSP.

3.3 MICRO GAS TURBINE

The micro gas turbine (μ GT) model is based on a simplified thermodynamic simulation of an air Brayton cycle. The pressure losses during the heat addition or friction losses of the fluid over the compressor and turbine (increased entropies) are quantified in terms of isentropic efficiencies for the compressor and the turbine.

3.3.1 Power calculation

The generated electrical power that is generated in the generator is calculated based on the power consumed in the compressor

$$P_{comp} = \dot{m} \cdot (h(T_{out,is,c}) - h(T_{in,c}))$$

and the mechanical power generated in the turbine.

$$P_{turb} = \dot{m} \cdot (h(T_{out,is,t}) - h(T_{in,t}))$$

In the model, the generator efficiency and the mechanical efficiency are used to calculate the electrical power output from the generator for the single-shaft μ GT.

$$P_{gen} = \eta_{gen} \cdot \left(P_{turb} - \frac{P_{comp}}{\eta_{mech}} \right)$$

For gas turbines, the power produced in the turbine and partly consumed by the compressor is proportional to the temperature of the fluid which passes through these components. The higher the turbine inlet temperature and pressure ratios are, the more specific power is produced at higher efficiencies. For every gas turbine there is one optimal operation point for which the turbomachinery was designed. This point is referred to as the design point. If the pressure ratios are increased further, the efficiency and specific power output will decrease again after the optimal operation point is surpassed. However, in reality, and especially for a solar operated system, the gas turbine will usually operate outside of the optimal point (“off-design”) for part-load conditions (Kohler 2019).

3.3.2 Off-design model

The design point performance analysis is straight forward as for this point the pressure ratios, efficiencies, the shaft speed, as well as the mass flow is known. Nevertheless, due to changes in the ambient conditions, power demand or variations in the turbine inlet temperature the gas turbine performance will deviate from the design point. This is referred to as off-design or part-load performance.

The off-design performance calculation is not straight forward as for the design point because it generally involves the iterative matching of many components (Kurzke und Halliwell 2018). Usually the information about the off-design behaviour of the compressor and turbine is provided in form of performance maps. The performance maps contain information about the relation of mass flow to pressure ratio and isentropic efficiencies.

The original model (see deliverables 7.1 and 7.2 for description) utilized performance maps for the compressor and the turbine to precisely determine the mass flow rate, compression-expansion ratio, and efficiencies of the two stages. However, this approach only considered one of the characteristic curves corresponding to the design speed of the μ GT (fixed shaft speed). As a result, all possible off-design operating scenarios for various speeds and the start-up/shut-down processes were not considered. Therefore, the modelled total electricity production of the system is expected to be more accurate when “off-design” scenarios are considered.

Additionally, the start-stop time of the μ GT was previously determined by the calculated sun position with respect to the location of the plant and did not consider the thermal power required by the turbine to operate. Previous simulations using this controller logic showed that the μ GT was activated for a short time before an energy balance was achieved, where the power supplied by the turbine was less than the power required by the compressor, which ultimately resulted in negative generation.

Literature shows several transient models for fuel-driven gas turbines where the rotation is initially provided by an electric motor and afterward is then entirely dependent on the mass flow of the fuel from the thermal power (Singh et al. 2018; Tsoutsanis und Meskin 2019). Based on this information, a new model was implemented for the μ GT where the rotational speed of the turbine is determined as a function of the thermal energy absorbed by the air receiver. Furthermore, the starting point of initializing the μ GT operation was selected according to the energy balance between the turbine and the compressor in order to minimize the use of the electric starter or the generator in electric motor mode and to only activate the turbine when positive electricity generation is achieved. Consequentially, an operation criterion (or “operating line”) for this model was determined where multiple steady state operation points are considered at different operating speeds according to the parameters of the previously utilized μ GT performance map. For a more detailed explanation of the model refer to (Rubio Cifuentes 2021).

3.3.3 Operating line and variable speed concept

The μ GT operation line is derived from a sequence of stable operating conditions for various gas turbine acceleration/deceleration paths under selected operation scenarios. The operation line was calculated using a performance map scaling tool developed within Fraunhofer ISE (Ferrerres 2021). This scaling tool can interpolate data from the existing characteristic curves of a performance map as well as can scale new performance maps to similar turbines. With the assumption that the frequency of generated electricity will be corrected by electronic power systems and that the turbine can operate at any speed, the scaling tool creates a path from the points of highest efficiency of the possible compressor speeds (ref. *Figure 4* and *Figure 5*). The required thermal power for the μ GT to be self-sustaining ($Power_{Turbine} = Power_{Compressor}$) as well as the heat required to reach the design operating point (Turbine Inlet Temperature = 750 °C) are calculated. With the required heat and the compressor operating characteristics (mass flow rate, pressure rate and efficiency) for the variable speeds known, three polynomials were created as a function of the heat input. In the function, the compressor characteristics are adjusted according to the heat captured by the Air Receiver for each simulation time step.

Figure 4: Proposed Operating line and comparison with previous model in a Pressure Ratio Performance Map

Figure 5: Proposed Operating line and comparison with previous model in a Efficiency Performance Map

3.4 HEAT EXCHANGER

The POLYPHEM prototype of the recovery heat exchanger was developed with specifications from AALBORG and KAEFER. The heat exchanger uses the exhaust gas from the micro gas turbine to heat up the thermal oil, which transfers the heat from the tower to the bottoming secondary oil loop with the TES and the ORC. The design is based on a counter-current heat exchanger with tubes in staggered arrangement and fins to increase the heat transfer to the thermal oil.

The heat transfer rate is calculated from the logarithmic mean temperature difference technique (Heat Atlas 2010) and the mass flow rate of the oil loop is calculated as a function of the input parameters. Since the proposed equations are cyclic, they are solved by iteratively.

3.5 ORGANIC RANKINE CYCLE

A black box model was used to implement the ORC unit. The equipment manufacturer and project partner ORCAN Energy provided a software to perform the simulations which allows a selection between two working fluids (R245fa or R1233zdE) and requires the heat supplied and the ambient temperature as input. The output it provides includes the net electricity production and the outlet temperature of the heat source fluid. By varying the heat input, this model enables the analysis of the ORC behaviour at partial load. The mathematical correlations for the electricity production calculation were obtained from this tool and implemented in ColSim CSP.

Additionally, this original ORC model was extended to scale the design size to larger capacities. For this purpose, it was necessary to create a polynomial with which the output temperature could be calculated as a function of the input heat and ambient temperature. Four sets of correlations were included in this model describing three reference ORC units of different capacity which can be used to design larger CSP plants.

3.6 STRATIFIED THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE

The stratified thermal storage consists of a single thermocline tank with a thermal separation of the hot and cold fluid, with solid-filler materials in place of high-cost heat transfer fluid (HTF) for further cost reduction.

The POLYPHEM thermal storage model was built upon a previously existing model. The purpose to further develop such model is to derive a more realistic model which correctly predicts the behaviour of such storage, to overcome several simulation limitations and to enhance its applicability.

In order to improve the storage model, the following improvements were required: a good computational efficiency, a flexible configuration concerning number and position of ports, a realistic implementation of the

involved physical phenomena and the suitability for annual simulations. This model also considers the resulting heat transfer with the tank wall which includes transient axial conduction and heat loss to the environment. Since it is considered as one of the major destratification factors, turbulent mixing is assumed near the inlets by using a turbulence factor. In case of inverse stratification, a propagation factor for the diffusive fluxes also allows a heat flux directed against the flow direction.

The following simplifications to the model were considered: The model uses the finite volume method of computational fluid dynamics for the modelling and solution of energy conservation equation and continuity equation (Seubert et al. 2014). The following simplifications to the model were considered:

- One-dimensional discretization of the fluid domain
- Detailed solution only of the energy equation
- Constant density and heat capacity for the solution of the energy equation
- Explicit forward time-stepping

The thermal energy storage model solves energy equations in one dimension. It can be categorized in three phases namely fluid, solid, walls. The governing convection-diffusion equation for the fluid phase is the following:

$$\varepsilon \rho_f c_{p_f} \left(\frac{\partial T_f}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial T_f}{\partial x} \right) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\lambda_f \frac{dT_f}{dx} \right) + UA_s (T_s - T_f) + UA_w (T_w - T_f)$$

For the solid phase the governing equation is

$$(1 - \varepsilon) \rho_s c_{p_s} \frac{\partial T_s}{\partial t} = UA_s (T_f - T_s)$$

and finally, the governing equation for the wall is

$$\rho_w c_{p_w} \frac{\partial T_w}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\lambda_w \frac{dT_w}{dx} \right) + U_{w,int} A_{w,int} (T_f - T_w) + U_{w,ext} A_{w,ext} (T_{amb} - T_w)$$

where subscript w refers to wall, h (W/m²K) is the corresponding heat transfer coefficient, A is the area, and ρ , c_p , ε and k are density, specific heat capacity, porosity, and thermal conductivity respectively. Temperature dependent fluid properties are considered and are updated at each simulation time step while the solid properties are considered constant. The heat transfer between HTF and solid, $h_{s,f}$, takes into account the convection heat transfer between thermal oil/concrete filler as well as thermal conduction inside the filler material. This convection heat transfer coefficient can be derived from different Nusselt number (Nu) correlations and the thermal conduction is corrected by considering the thermal conduction resistance of the solid filler. A detailed description of the model can be found in (Bhanderi 2021).

4. PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT AND VALIDATION

4.1 HELIOSTAT FIELD MODEL

4.1.1 Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis was performed to assess the impact of the tower height and the distance to the first row of mirrors on the optical efficiency of the heliostat field. The variables under analysis are listed in **Table 1**, together with the default values and the ranges used for the analysis. These default values represent the THEMIS site from where the specified ranges have been considered.

Parameter	Description	Default value	Variation	
			Range	Unit
H_{tower}	Tower height	100	[25-175]	m
$d_{hf,min}$	Distance from the tower to the first row of mirrors	50	[25-75]	m

Table 1: Parameters for the sensitivity analysis of the heliostat field

A visualisation of the resulting optical efficiency is shown in **Figure 6**, where the default values are represented in the centre of the normalized parameter axis. These default values were obtained from a model to design utility-scale power plants, that implemented a correlation based on existing commercial systems. Thus, the obtained results indicate that other simulation tools are required for small-scale power plants. It is observed that – for POLYPHEM prototype size – lower tower height and smaller distances from the tower to the first row of the mirrors present a better optical efficiency. Moreover, for the tower height, the presence of an optimal value is observed.

In the case of the distance between the tower and the first row of heliostat mirrors, the efficiency increases when shortening this distance (also observed in (Collado und Guallar 2019; Collado und Guallar 2012)). Therefore, the minimum radius of the first row of the heliostat field should be the smallest possible ensuring that there are not any mechanical collisions between two adjacent mirrors. Nevertheless, it should be mentioned that the shading of the tower is not considered in heliostat field design model, so including this in the calculations could have an impact in the results obtained.

Figure 6: Sensitivity analysis for the optical efficiency at design point

4.1.2 Heliostat field design calculation

To further compare these heliostat fields, the layout of the mirrors together with their design point efficiencies were plotted. From the initial oversized heliostat field, the selected mirrors are shown in **Figure 7** for a 40 m and 100 m tower height respectively. The empty dots represent the discarded mirrors, whereas the coloured ones represent the selected ones and their efficiency.

Figure 7: POLYPHEM - Heliostat field layout and optical efficiency for 40 m (left) and 100 m (right) tower heights. Attention: colour ranges for optical efficiency are not equal!

4.1.3 Performance evaluation

The distribution of solar radiation flux on the absorber surfaces of the receiver was modelled with ray tracing for the optimized heliostat field layout. All heliostats aim at the center of the billboard receiver. The resulting flux maps on the pressurized air receiver surface for two exemplary DNI values from the annually optimized heliostat field is shown in **Figure 8**.

Figure 8: POLYPHEM - Resulting flux concentration map in the receiver surface for two exemplary moments of low DNI (left) and high DNI (right)

4.2 PRESSURIZED AIR RECEIVER MODEL

4.2.1 Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis was performed to evaluate how different variables may affect the pressure drop and the wall temperature in the receiver. The analysis was done by changing one variable at a time with the variables and their variation ranges listed in **Table 2**. These default values represent a POLYPHEM prototype size receiver, from where a 50% variation was performed to reach the limits of the simulated ranges.

Results are shown in **Figure 9**, where default values are represented in the centre of the normalized parameter axis. In case of the POLYPHEM prototype, 16 500 Pa is the maximum allowable pressure drop. It is found that – without the insert tapes – the pressure drop is far below the limit for the default values. It increases when the number of tubes or the inner diameter decreases, because of the increased fluid velocity inside the tubes. However, if the twisted tape inserts are considered, the friction factor is higher, so for the

same receiver geometry, the pressure drop is also higher, increasing rapidly to the maximum allowable value when varying parameters.

Parameter	Description	Default value	Variation	Unit
			Range	
n_{tube}	Number of tubes	763	[381-1144]	-
l_{tube}	Length of the tubes	1	[0.5-1.5]	m
d_{inner}	Inner diameter	0.006	[0.003-0.009]	m
l_{twist}	Length of the insert for a 180° twist	0.015	[0.0075-0.025]	m
δ	Thickness of the insert	0.0006	[0.0003-0.0009]	m
n_{row}	Number of rows if tubes	7	[3-11]	-
n_{tube}	Number of tubes	763	[381-1144]	-
l_{tube}	Length of the tubes	1	[0.5-1.5]	m
d_{inner}	Inner diameter	0.006	[0.003-0.009]	m
l_{twist}	Length of the insert for a 180° twist	0.015	[0.0075-0.025]	m
δ	Thickness of the insert	0.0006	[0.0003-0.0009]	m

Table 2: Parameters for the sensitivity analysis of the solar receiver

Figure 9: Sensitivity analysis for the pressure drop in the POLYPHEM receiver without twisted tapes (left) and with twisted tapes (right).

Figure 10: Sensitivity analysis for wall temperature in the POLYPHEM receiver without twisted tapes (left) and with twisted tapes (right).

In the same way, as for the pressure drop, a sensitivity analysis was performed to evaluate the wall temperature (**Figure 10**). In this case, without the insert tapes, the maximum allowable temperature of 1000°C is exceeded even for the default values. However, when considering the twisted tape insert, this temperature is lowered to an acceptable range due to the enhancement of the heat transfer. This result demonstrates that the technology would not be feasible without the heat transfer enhancement of the twisted tape inserts. It can be observed that the most relevant variables for the wall temperature are the number of tubes, the length of the tubes, and the number of rows. Therefore, for the design approach, those variables were taken as degrees of freedom.

4.2.2 Performance evaluation

In order to evaluate the performance of the receiver, several possible geometries of the receiver fulfilling the three main constraints, each having a different length of the tubes, number of tubes, and number of rows. In **Figure 11**, **Figure 12** and **Figure 13** results from simulations for tube lengths of 0.9 m and 1 m, several numbers of tubes and number of rows are shown.

In **Figure 11**, each dot represents a possible combination of the total number of tubes and number of rows, and the colour represents the pressure drop of each receiver. Similarly, in **Figure 12**, each dot indicates a combination of the number of tubes and number of rows, but in this case, the colour represents the maximum wall temperature, while in **Figure 13** the colour is an indicator of the efficiency of the receiver. Each possible combination leads to a different pressure drop, heat transfer and heat losses, thus, the pressure, wall temperature, and efficiency are different for each geometry.

The effect of the imposed constraints is evident in the results. It is observed that the pressure drop is independent of the number of rows. In addition, it determines the minimum number of tubes in the receiver for not exceeding the maximum pressure drop. The reason behind this is that decreasing the number of tubes will increase the speed of the air inside the tubes, and since the mass flow rate would remain constant, this increase of the speed leads to an increase in pressure drop. It is also confirmed that the minimum number of tubes is higher for long tubes.

Figure 11: Pressured drop for different total number of tubes and rows for 0.9 m tube length (left) and 1 m tube length (right)

Additionally, in **Figure 12**, it is found that having more rows increases the wall temperature, as thermal resistance of the receiver increases when adding rows. Therefore, for solutions with a low number of tubes but a large number of rows, the maximum wall temperature constraint is exceeded. At the same time, in the right lower part of the figures, the aspect ratio constraint limits the possible results. A large number of tubes with few rows will result in a very wide receiver. Since the aspect ratio has to be around 1, the number of tubes will therefore increase as the number of rows increase.

Figure 12: Maximum wall temperature for different total number of tubes and rows for 0.9 m tube length (left) and 1 m tube length (right)

Figure 13: POLYPHEM Receiver efficiency for different total number of tubes and rows for 0.9 m tube length (left) and 1 m tube length (right).

In **Figure 13** the variation of the thermal efficiency for different geometries is shown. The most efficient results are small geometries with high wall temperature, since the thermal resistance is lower for these cases. Nevertheless, it should be noted that the efficiency relative variation is not larger than 6%.

It is observed that heliostat mirrors closer to the tower present the highest efficiencies for both layouts. The reason for this lies in the increment of absorption losses and spillage losses when increasing the distance to the receiver. On the other hand, for mirrors with the same distance to the receiver, the central ones have a better efficiency due to the cosine factor loss, which is higher in the corners of the heliostat field.

For the optimized receiver, **Figure 14** displays exemplary distributions of pressurized air bulk, pressurized air film and absorber surface temperature, for the radiation concentration resulting from the heliostat field model. The radiation distribution, and consequently also the temperature distributions, is very symmetric on the panels. The bulk temperature distribution visualizes the flow, with temperature increasing from the inlet of the tubes onwards. With the radiation concentration being highest on the central absorber areas, the bulk temperature increase along the fluid flow in the outer tubes is less than in the central tubes. Unfortunately, since the receiver could not become operational within the timeframe of the project, the receiver model could not be validated with experimental data of the developed receiver.

date: May 27, time: 09:01:00
 DNI: 915.0, max. conc.: 255.4, mean conc.: 213.3

date: May 27, time: 12:51:00
 DNI: 932.4, max. conc.: 493.4, mean conc.: 369.8

Figure 14: Distributions of the pressurized air bulk temperature, pressurized air film temperature, absorber surface temperature, and radiation concentration on the front surface for the optimized POLYPHEM receiver configuration for two exemplary moments of low DNI (left) and high DNI (right).

4.3 MICRO GAS TURBINE MODEL

4.3.1 Performance map review

The algorithm developed at Fraunhofer ISE can construct an extended performance map which obtains the performance parameters at any required turbine-compressor shaft speed, which is fundamental in a variable speed approach used in this work. The algorithm produces the coefficients to reconstruct a characteristic curve (ellipsoid) of each speed which then allows the calculation of the mass flow rate, pressure rate and the efficiency of the compressor. A review was performed to compare the extended performance map with the previous model (Ferreres 2021), the data provided by the manufacturer, and the experimental results provided by the μ GT supplier. **Figure 15** and **Figure 16** show the comparison between the characteristic curve generated and the data provided by the manufacturer/ μ GT supplier.

Figure 15: Comparison of the performance map data used in the model and the data provided by the manufacturer.

Figure 16: Comparison of the performance map data used in the model and the experimental data provided by the supplier of the μ GT.

4.3.2 Performance evaluation and validation

The model allows simulating the response of the μ GT to the variation of the input heat rate and ambient temperature. The implemented variable speed approach indicates the change in μ GT performance parameters that are extracted from the performance map. The simulated operating parameters of the μ GT are given in **Figure 17** as a function of the thermal energy absorbed by the air (HTF) inside the Brayton cycle. As the heat rate absorption increases, the turbine accelerates to the maximum safe operating speed.

Figure 17: POLYPHEM - μ GT performance parameters as a function of heat rate absorbed.

To test the results of the developed thermodynamic model of the μ GT the commercial software EBSILON® Professional (Ebsilon) was used. Multiple simulations were performed in Ebsilon and in ColSim CSP using the performance data from the operating lines to compare the simulated parameters i.e. the power consumed by the compressor, power provided by the turbine and the electric power delivered by the generator as shown in **Figure 18**.

Figure 18: POLYPHEM - Comparison of the calculation obtained in ColSim CSP and Ebsilon of the power of μ GT subcomponents under variable speed approach.

4.4 HEAT EXCHANGER MODEL

To evaluate the performance of the RHX, the component model was tested separately through simulation with two pre-defined conditions namely design and off-design conditions. The results of the performance evaluation are shown in **Figure 19** for the design point model and **Figure 20** for the off-design point model. For the design point simulation, the air mass flow is constant at 0.82 kg/s while the gas turbine is running. The oil cycle is running as long as the gas turbine outlet temperature is high enough to reach 300°C of oil temperature at the outlet of the heat exchanger, by adapting the oil mass flow in the primary oil cycle (in [POLYPHEM_D7.3_Performance assessment and model validation](#)

grey). For the off-design model, the air mass flow is adapted to the outlet temperature of the micro gas turbine.

Figure 19: Result of the design point simulation of RHX for two exemplary days.

Figure 20: Result of the off-design point simulation of RHX for two exemplary days

4.5 ORGANIC RANKINE CYCLE MODEL

The black box model implemented for the ORC calculates the electricity produced as a function of the ambient temperature and the rate of heat supplied. The heat input rate varies depending on the availability and/or demand profile as shown in **Figure 21**. The outlet temperature of the oil from the ORC must be within a limited range since the cold fluid is fed back into the thermocline TES. A correlation was included in the model to consider varying inlet temperatures into the ORC, allowing the inlet temperature to drop below 105°C when there is a low heat feed rate. When the ORC operates at full load from the TES, the heat delivered is constant, however the ambient temperature effects the ORC efficiency between 6.32% and 7.44% , affecting the power output (**Figure 22**).

Figure 21: POLYPHEM - ORC performance in response to variation of Input thermal power. Fluctuation is due to change in ambient temperature.

Figure 22: POLYPHEM - ORC performance as a function of ambient temperature

4.6 STRATIFIED THERMAL STORAGE MODEL

The stratified thermal storage data was validated with Microsol-R test facility (CNRS/PROMES, France) provided by CNRS for the range of operating conditions, validation of the model has been performed for the storage with structured filler arrangement. The filler bed used for POLYPHEM is a vertical stack of steel baskets with concrete filler bricks arranged inside each basket. The heat transfer fluid used for this application is the thermal oil Jarytherm DBT[®], which is flowing through the hollow channels of brick.

Heat transfer coefficient between thermal oil and concrete filler material is calculated based on Nu correlation given by Gnielinski (Gnielinski 2006). The following adaptation of the Nu number value had to be considered for the simulations presented here in order to fit the experimental data:

Oil Flow	$Nu_{Modification}$
Charge	$Nu_{Calculated} * 3$
Discharge	$Nu_{Calculated} * 4$

Table 3: Parameter modification for modelling dual-media region (TES zone only).

This modification can be partially explained by non-uniform geometry inside dual-media region (there are purely liquid zones in between each filler baskets, and also between tank walls and filler baskets) and the influence this may have on heat transfer and fluid flow behaviours. Additional surface area in gaps between the filler bricks and the relative rough surface of the pipes are other possible reasons for the necessary adaption on the correlation. Except the Nusselt number modification in **Table 3** to calculate heat transfer, all other parameters given in **Table 4** are based on the dual media region of the TES zone.

ID	Parameter	Values TES zone	Values Storage Tank	Unit
1	Diameter of tank	1.276	1.276	m
2	Height of tank	2.5	2.85	m
3	Volume of storage	3.197	3.644	m ³
4	Porosity	0.443	0.512	-
5	Wall thickness	0.008	0.008	m
6	Conductivity of wall	30	30	W/m-K
7	Cp of wall	500	500	J/kg-K
8	Density of wall	8000	8000	kg/m ³
9	Insulation thickness	0.255	0.255	m
10	Conductivity of insulation	0.086	0.086	W/m-K
11	Ambient temperature	15	15	°C

Table 4: Simulation parameters for validation of the stratified thermal storage with Microsol-R data.

The results of the comparison of the simulations performed with different operating conditions for charging and discharging processes are promising. **Figure 23** and **Figure 24** show the comparison between the experimental (continuous lines) and the simulated temperature evolution (crossed lines) at the centre axis of the tank over the duration of a charging process. The validation study for charging shows that the simulation results are in close agreement with experimental results in terms of thermal front velocity and axial temperature profile inside the storage. The validation study for the discharge run also shows that simulation results are in good agreement with experimental ones in terms of discharge duration (for more detailed comparison refer to Deliverable 3.5).

To model the heat transfer between oil and concrete brick in a discharging process, it is required to apply a different modification rule than the one applied to charging process. However, the same modification rule is applied to all discharge simulations. In **Figure 24**, the thickness of thermocline is slightly higher in simulation profiles compared to experimental ones. In addition to that, the discrepancy between the two profiles is slightly higher in the higher temperature region of the tank which is possibly due to different hydraulic structures of storage at the inlet/outlet and assumption of 1-D flow behaviour in the simulation. The storage filler bed contains pure liquid zones between baskets which cause a time delay in the movement of the thermal front, and the thermal behaviour can be visualized by the oscillations towards left side in charging experimental profiles and towards right side in discharging experimental profiles.

For the charging process, the implemented correlation leads to the correct estimation of heat transfer after applying a modification factor. Therefore, the correlation can be regarded as valid since it estimates the correct heat transfer variables for the Reynolds and Prandtl number. Similar justification is also valid for the discharging process. The basis behind different Nu modification factors for charging and discharging in the model, is the observed storage thermal behaviours in charging and discharge operation in the experimental test. These findings could be the basis to predict the future behaviour of a corresponding real size storage.

Figure 23: Validation with experimental data of the charging process from 180°C to 250°C with mass flow of 0.2 kg/s (top left), 0.3 kg/s (top right), 0.45 kg/s (bottom left) and 0.9 kg/s (bottom right).

Figure 24: Validation with experimental data of the discharging process from 180°C to 110°C with mass flow of 0.2 kg/s (top left), 0.9 kg/s (top right), 0.4 kg/s (bottom left) and 0.6 kg/s (bottom right).

5. CONCLUSION

Component design models and design tool were developed for every component of the POLYPHEM plant. These models are the basis for designing the plant which are prerequisites for evaluating the optical performance of the heliostat field, simulating the annual performance of the complete system model, and performing the techno-economic optimization (Task 7.2). The developed components include:

- A detailed micro gas turbine model which can simulate the behaviour of a micro-gas turbine/compressor including a variable speed approach to simulate the partial load and start-up and ramp-down procedures.
- A detailed heliostat field model using the in-house ray tracing tool which provides the system simulation software with an input file containing the annual concentration factors.
- A pressurized air receiver model which allows for a flexible combination of different components such as tubes, panels, splitters, mixers, or passive surfaces based on the design from CEA. The thermo-hydraulic receiver model makes use of transient flux maps on receiver surfaces and considers natural and forced convection in the cavity.
- An air/oil heat exchanger for the RHX based on the design from AALBORG and KAEFER, and a heat transfer coefficient from literature and a constant pressure loss from experimental tests.
- An ORC model based on polynomials for output power and outlet oil temperature extracted from the simulation tool of ORCAN (ORC manufacturer).
- A validated model of stratified thermal energy storage using measurement data provided by CNRS.

The performance of all components was adjusted and optimized with the inputs of the project partners, refining the component model results. However, due to delays in the measurements in WP6 (Task 6.4), the component models could not be validated with experimental data from the demonstration plant as components of a whole system. However, the simulation models of the key components were validated using isolated component tests data, data from the manufacturer, or another simulation software. Particularly the project made it possible to validate the stratified thermal storage model based on experimental data provided by CNRS of the already existing Microsol-R test facility, as well as the micro gas turbine based on isolated test runs at KAEFER and against Epsilon software, and the ORC based on the input provided by the manufacturer. For the stratified thermal energy storage model, as one of the innovative components of POLYPHEM, simulation results show a very good agreement with experimental results (after adjustment), concluding that the behaviour of such storage can be simulated with the numerical model developed at Fraunhofer ISE.

These components were integrated into a simulation model in ColSimCSP, Fraunhofer ISE's in-house simulation tool, and different operation strategies were built upon customized operation modes. Due to the previously mentioned delays, the validation of the simulation model as a whole plant could not be verified. However, through the validation of single components, the uncertainty of the modelling is not expected to be unacceptable.

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